

Path2Integrity questionnaire for students with an academic degree and researchers (graduates)

Instructions

During this evaluation, we kindly ask you to respond to the following case scenarios about research practices. Each case scenario starts with a short description followed by 4 steps which build on one another. Only one option can be chosen for each question.

First decide which action is in line with good research practices and then use the slider to indicate how confident you feel about your answer.

Please choose a reason for your answer by choosing the option that best suits your opinion and then use the slider to indicate how confident you feel about your answer.

Please note that you cannot return to a previous page of the survey! But you may always skip a question, stop the survey, or withdraw from it completely.

For her first research project at the university, Olivia wants to ensure that she knows how exactly research should be done and what considerations she has to take into account. To follow good research practices Olivia ...

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- reviews what she has been taught in high-school.
- just starts and learns by doing it.
- looks for examples in the press.
- looks at the university's guidelines for good research practices.

How confident are you about your answer?

Please enter a value between 1 and 100, where 1 stands for very unsure and 100 for very confident.

- |very unsure|very confident

Olivia's decision complies with good research practices because ...

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- it ensures reliable research results.
- everyone does it like this.
- research must not be restricted by rules.
- it saves valuable resources.

How confident are you about your answer?

Please enter a value between 1 and 100, where 1 stands for very unsure and 100 for very confident.

- |very unsure|very confident

Salim has conducted interviews for his research project on misconduct at the university. He found that at least some of his colleagues had used questionable research practices. When he presents the first results at an internal colloquium, a discussion is sparked on how to proceed with this knowledge. To follow good research practices, Salim ...

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- should listen to all points of view and then decide according to his own convictions.
- should stop the discussion.
- should not have presented the results at all.
- should listen to all points of view, weigh them up, and decide on the basis of the best arguments.

How confident are you about your answer?

Please enter a value between 1 and 100, where 1 stands for very unsure and 100 for very confident.

- |very unsure|very confident

Salim's action is in line with good research practices because ...

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- this decision allows him to justify his analysis step by step.
- this decision ensures equal treatment in research.
- it is the duty of Salim to answer the questions.
- there are no relevant binding codes and regulations that say otherwise.

How confident are you about your answer?

Please enter a value between 1 and 100, where 1 stands for very unsure and 100 for very confident.

- |very unsure|very confident

David wants to conduct a research project but realises that there are many different methods mentioned in the literature. To ensure good research practices, David should ...

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- use the method that seems most appropriate for his research.
- use the method with which he is most familiar.
- use the method that is most commonly used.
- use the most prestigious method.

How confident are you about your answer?

Please enter a value between 1 and 100, where 1 stands for very unsure and 100 for very confident.

- |very unsure|very confident

David's decision is in line with good research practices because ...

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- the majority does so and David must follow.
- it ensures responsible conduct of research.
- it is the duty of David to do so.
- since there are no binding regulations, he can do so.

How confident are you about your answer?

Please enter a value between 1 and 100, where 1 stands for very unsure and 100 for very confident.

- |very unsure|very confident

Ahmed has observed his fellow researcher Susie falsifying data in a research project. Ahmed wants to follow good research practices and informs the ...

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- ombudsperson.
- police.
- ethics committee.
- public relations department.

How confident are you about your answer?

Please enter a value between 1 and 100, where 1 stands for very unsure and 100 for very confident.

- |very unsure|very confident

Ahmed's decision is in line with good research practices because ...

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- it ensures equal treatment of all misconduct cases.
- it complies with codes and regulations in research.
- it is Ahmed's duty.
- it protects the reputation of Ahmed's organisation.

How confident are you about your answer?

Please enter a value between 1 and 100, where 1 stands for very unsure and 100 for very confident.

- |very unsure|very confident

Ivana is invited to be a member of the research integrity committee. She is asked to participate in hearings on a new misconduct case. To act in accordance with good research practices, Ivana accepts the invitation because...

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- she has experience.
- she is impartial.
- she often does voluntary work.
- she knows the case well.

How confident are you about your answer?

Please enter a value between 1 and 100, where 1 stands for very unsure and 100 for very confident.

- |very unsure|very confident

Ivana's decision is in line with good research practices because ...

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- it helps ensure the reliability of research results.
- it will decrease the damage to the university from having a case of misconduct.
- this decision ensures equal treatment of research.
- it will enhance her reputation to do so.

How confident are you about your answer?

Please enter a value between 1 and 100, where 1 stands for very unsure and 100 for very confident.

- |very unsure|very confident

Bill, who is from a Greek university, is collaborating with Lorenzo, the research project leader, who is from a university in Finland. Their institutions follow different codes of conduct. To follow good research practices, they ...

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- both use the code of their own institution.
- have to use the code applicable to the project leader.
- must opt for the stricter code.
- agree on a code that applies for both of them.

How confident are you about your answer?

Please enter a value between 1 and 100, where 1 stands for very unsure and 100 for very confident.

- |very unsure|very confident

Their decision is in line with good research practices, because ...

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- this ensures collaborative work in research.
- as the majority does so, they have to follow this practice.
- this decision ensures equal treatment in research.
- the legal framework does not allow them to act in any other way.

How confident are you about your answer?

Please enter a value between 1 and 100, where 1 stands for very unsure and 100 for very confident.

- |very unsure|very confident

Sven wants to write a paper for a journal regarding his research project. For this he is going to paraphrase from other texts. To follow good research practices, Sven refers to the original source ...

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- with a reference at the end of the paraphrased section.
- by enclosing the section in quotation marks.
- by using quotation marks and a reference at the end of the quote.
- only with a reference in the bibliography at the end of the paper.

How confident are you about your answer?

Please enter a value between 1 and 100, where 1 stands for very unsure and 100 for very confident.

- |very unsure|very confident

Sven's decision is in line with good research practices, because ...

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- as the majority does so, Sven also has to follow this practice.
- this ensures recognition of the source and the original author.
- this decision ensures equal treatment in research.
- there are no relevant binding codes and regulations.

How confident are you about your answer?

Please enter a value between 1 and 100, where 1 stands for very unsure and 100 for very confident.

- |very unsure|very confident

Gabriela is writing a paper about her research project for a journal. For this, she wants to use the description of the content that she has written for a previous paper. To follow good research practices, Gabriela ...

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- must rewrite the part from the earlier paper.
- can reuse her own work without citing herself.
- has to ask the journal editor for permission to quote it.
- should quote the part from the earlier paper or cite herself.

How confident are you about your answer?

Please enter a value between 1 and 100, where 1 stands for very unsure and 100 for very confident.

- |very unsure|very confident

Gabriela's decision is in line with good research practices because ...

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- it ensures the appropriate presentation of the source and the original author.
- the majority observes this practice and Gabriela also has to follow it.
- it is Gabriela's duty to do so.
- since there are no binding regulations, she can do as she wishes.

How confident are you about your answer?

Please enter a value between 1 and 100, where 1 stands for very unsure and 100 for very confident.

- |very unsure|very confident

Elena conducts interviews with teachers from a local school. She remembers that Professor Aya said something about the storage of data. To ensure that she works according to good research practices, Elena has to store ...

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- all data necessary for traceability.
- all data concerning her research.
- only personal data.
- all data relevant for publication.

How confident are you about your answer?

Please enter a value between 1 and 100, where 1 stands for very unsure and 100 for very confident.

- |very unsure|very confident

Elena's decision is in line with good research practices because ...

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- due to the complexity and variety of research, it must be done this way.
- it is the duty of Elena to follow this process.
- the legal framework governing universities requires it.
- it ensures reliable research results.

How confident are you about your answer?

Please enter a value between 1 and 100, where 1 stands for very unsure and 100 for very confident.

- |very unsure|very confident

Amar will publish a paper on the results of research by an international working group in which he participates. Before the project started, all of the group members agreed to work transparently and openly. To follow good research practices in collaborative working groups, he ...

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- needs the approval of the paper from all project partners.
- must get feedback and reviews from all project partners before publishing.
- notifies the others after the publication.
- informs the others about his plans before the publication.

How confident are you about your answer?

Please enter a value between 1 and 100, where 1 stands for very unsure and 100 for very confident.

- |very unsure|very confident

Amar's decision is in line with good research practices because ...

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- since the group agreed on transparency and acting in this way ensures responsible research.
- it is the Amar's duty to do so.
- only by doing so, Amar can ensure the greatest possible benefit for the working group.
- the group agreed on transparency but it has no other binding obligations.

How confident are you about your answer?

Please enter a value between 1 and 100, where 1 stands for very unsure and 100 for very confident.

- |very unsure|very confident